

FUNCTIONAL AND STYLISTIC FEATURES OF NEWSPAPER HEADLINES: BASED ON BRITISH NEWSPAPERS

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Abstract. This article discusses the goals and tasks of the editor of the newspaper headline, language units in increasing the language appeal of the newspaper speech. Language policy, in turn, aims to develop a style that has a reinforcing effect on the audience.

Keywords: newspaper, headline, language, readers, journalist, informative.

ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНО-СТИЛИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ГАЗЕТНЫХ ЗАГОЛОВКОВ: НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ БРИТАНСКИХ ГАЗЕТ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются цели и задачи редактора газетного заголовка, языковых единиц в повышении языковой привлекательности газетной речи. Языковая политика, в свою очередь, направлена на выработку стиля, оказывающего подкрепляющее воздействие на аудиторию.

Ключевые слова: газета, заголовок, язык, читатели, журналист, информативность.

The goals and objectives of the headline compiler are determined by the discourse of the newspaper, its language policy. The language policy, in turn, is aimed at developing a style that can have a consolidating effect on the audience. This style is the result of a complex process of reaching a consensus between the newspaper as a social institution and its readers. In working on it, journalists often turn to psychology for help. In particular, they are guided by the peculiarities of the mentality of the readers of their newspaper, which allows them to find a common language with them, which is necessary to create a favorable "background of predictability", that is, the prerequisites for reading. Most researchers see the task of the headline journalist as capturing the attention of the audience and reflecting the content of the text. Depending on which of these two tasks is preferred, as well as depending on the means used by the journalist to achieve them, headlines are divided into five types:

1) informative; 2) attractive; 3) informative and attractive; 4) disorientation; 5) defective.

Informative headlines are compiled by the journalist for the sole purpose of giving as much information as possible about the content and/or topic of the text. Most often, informative titles are verb constructions: a sentence with a simple verbal predicate, a two-part sentence with a nominal predicate, a two-part sentence with a complex verbal predicate, an indefinitely personal sentence.

This type of headlines is primarily characteristic of the style of the English business and socio-political press. In English journalism, it is most often found in quality newspapers, as well as news reports in the mainstream press.

Attractive headlines are designed to encourage readers to purchase a product or service. They act as an advertising constant and resemble promotional offers.

Attractive headlines are most often found in the press of mass culture, information and advertising and socio-political publications. On the pages of English newspapers, the predicate in attractive headlines is often expressed by the verb in the form of the present continuous tense. At

the same time, they contain such grammatical elements as the first person pronoun *T* and the auxiliary verb 'am', which are usually absent in other models. The same grammatical features are characteristic of the multi-sentence headlines most commonly found on Daily Mail pages. Attractive headlines became more common in the mid-90s. By the end of the period we are considering, however, the share of this type of headlines on the pages of British newspapers has decreased.

Informative-attractive headings combine the features of informative and attractive headings. They often use lexical and syntactic stylistic devices and means. In the second half of the 80s and in the 90s, they most often used phraseological units, metaphor, catachresis, colloquial words and expressions, syntactic models that have the greatest stylistic marking.

The perception of these headlines in the period under consideration was often complicated by the following factors: 1) congestion with punctuation marks; 2) abuse of foreign language inclusions; 3) mismatch heading style and genre of the text.

During the period under consideration, headlines of this type have become more frequent in British newspapers than before.

Headings of a misleading type are designed to mislead readers about the content of the heading text. In the second half of the 80s and in the 90s, the following types of misleading headlines were most common:

1. Headlines with minimal predictability. Such headings are associated not so much with the text as with the subtext of the articles, and even more often with an extra-textual situation. They received the greatest prevalence on the pages of "MK" and "Megapolis-Express".

2. Headings representing one of the abstracts of the publication. Such headings usually do not reflect the essence of the text, and sometimes even contradict it. However, they are expressive and intriguing.

3. Headlines, which are a direct distortion, juggling of the facts contained in the text. This group is the most numerous in modern newspapers.

Researchers explain the popularity of these headlines by the desire of journalists to make the headline interesting for the reader at all costs, even if they have nothing to say to the latter. A more important reason for the spread of misleading headlines is, in our opinion, a change in the mentality of the readership, as a result of which there was an imbalance between the rational-logical and emotional-figurative orientation in favor of the latter. This, in turn, led to an uncritical attitude towards the information contained in the header.

Finally, headlines are defective if they contain a stylistic error that interferes with the perception of the text and forms a negative attitude towards it on the part of the reader. The meaning of headings of this type often remains unclear even after reading the text. The phenomenon of "defective" headers is not new. Their distribution reflects the carelessness, slovenliness of the language, the preference for content and form, characteristic of British newspapers of the period we are considering. The distribution of headlines of this type was also facilitated by the involvement in journalistic activities of people who do not have a special education.

The headlines of the second half of the 1980s and 1990s could not but reflect those socio-economic, socio-political, structural, functional and typological changes, which in their scale and consequences were in many respects similar to the global transformations of the 20s of the XX

century. . As a result of these changes, a new communicative situation has arisen, the worldview of the readership has changed

Such changes are evidenced, in particular, by the functioning of newspaper headlines during this period. So, the major, optimistic modality characteristic of them in the second half of the 80s gradually gave way to a minor, pessimistic and, in a number of newspapers, reckless, slyly aggressive (banter). At the same time, headlines were circulating, deliberately misleading readers about the content of the text. They differ from all the previously described types in that, despite the effect of deceived expectation they create, they do not arouse a negative attitude among readers. This, in particular, is evidenced by their prevalence in the period under review. Thus, this phenomenon reflects changes in the mentality of the readership, namely, the imbalance of the rational-logical orientation towards the emotional-figurative one, which explains the uncritical attitude to the information contained in the publication and, in particular, in the title. The emergence of this type of headlines also reflects the intensified struggle of periodicals for readers, as a result of which journalists are looking for new ways to attract attention. This led to a significant increase in the role of the attractive component and the frequency of advertising and expressive-evaluative titles. The most common means of attracting attention during this period were parallel constructions of various kinds. At the same time, the headlines of the 80s and 90s actively combined various phonetic and syntactic devices, thanks to which they were able to reproduce those components that usually accompany oral speech: cheerfulness and lethargy, energy and inertia, determination and timidity, interest and indifference. Journalists used them to influence their audience, trying to evoke the desired emotional and volitional reaction from readers. The functions of the newspaper headline in relation to the text have changed markedly. So, if in the early 80s the headings basically did not fully reflect the semantic component of the text, then by the second half of the 90s they became more informative. Complex headings, which were previously often found with publications of informative genres and served to help readers better understand the composition of the text, have practically fallen out of use. Changes in the functioning of newspaper headlines are closely related to changes in their syntactic structure. This is evidenced, in particular, by the fact that in order to distinguish headings - incomplete sentences, the prevalence of which in the period of time we are considering can only be compared with their popularity in the 20s, from nominative sentences with an inconsistent definition with the main member, it is necessary to take into account that the function that the heading performs in the text. The reason for this is that the process of perception by readers of a newspaper headline goes through several stages, and the understanding of the headline before and after reading the text is usually different. The main change at the level of syntax was the prominence of verb constructions, the frequency of which increased from 17.84% in 1987 to 39.65% in 1997. The main reason for this is the desire to make headlines as informative as possible. In addition, verbal constructions compare favorably with nominative ones in that they are aimed at characterizing the current process, state. The capacity and ambiguity of verb forms makes headings more expressive. A significant factor that influenced the change in the communicative situation and the consciousness of the audience was the influence of the Anglo-American culture, expressed, in particular, in a multi-level borrowing from the English language.

As in English titles, it was actively used to 1) denote actions that coincide with the moment of speech, occurring in the past and in the future; 2) engaging readers in action; 3) Headline messages with a touch of impartiality and relevance.

A feature of the use of this model in British newspapers is the significantly greater prevalence of the present extended actual (or present extended concrete) tense, which makes up 49% of all headlines with a predicate expressed in the form of the present tense. In British headlines, this indicator is much lower - 9.2%, which is partly due to the presence in English of an alternative form of expressing the present actual time through Present Continuous (Present Continuous). The real abstract, or "the present of eternal truths", denoting a repetitive, ordinary, typical action, presented in the broad sense of the present tense and not connected with the moment of speech, has also become much more widespread in English headlines. 12% of headlines with a predicate, expressed verb in the present tense have this meaning, compared to 4.6% in British newspapers.

In contrast, headlines with the verb in the present historical tense form are more common in English headlines (43.74% of all uses of the present tense compared to 30% in British newspapers).

Some features in the use of syntactic models are associated with differences in the system of grammatical categories and their morphological expression in both languages. Thus, headlines with a predicate, an expressed verb in the form of a passive voice and a short participle of the passive voice of the past tense make up the fourth most common group in English headlines (8.6% of all headlines), while headlines of this type in British newspapers make up only 3.6%. This is explained by the fact that in English passive forms are used in cases where a person or object in the function of the subject is affected by someone else.

During the period under consideration, connecting structures became widespread, which made up the fourth most common model in British headlines. Usually their role is to communicate stylistic information. They are often used to create the effect of surprise, unpredictability, which is achieved by expressive isolating part of the statement. Perhaps the distribution of headlines of this model in newspapers is explained precisely by the penetration of newspaper genres of colloquial speech into the stylistic system. Attaching constructions have both great communicative and emotionally expressive possibilities. They allow journalists to report maximum information with a minimum of linguistic means. Connective constructions are promising in terms of their communicative capabilities, as they allow you to increase the information content of the statement and draw the attention of readers to that part of it that might have been left without proper attention. The two most representative types of this model are a) segmented structures and b) parceled structures.

The popularity of parceled structures is partly due to their ability to be divided into any number of parts that retain the same relationships among themselves that are observed in an undivided structure. This allows you to give the statement a completely unexpected, sometimes paradoxical look. In addition, the structural advantage of this model is its ability to subject the heading to inversion, to put it in a distant position relative to the main part of the sentence. From a functional point of view, the headings of this model allow the journalist to draw the attention of readers to that part of the statement that would have been left without due attention if the heading structure had been standard. During the period under review, their use has increased.

This is partly due to the automation of the production process, as it allows journalists to save mental energy, their time and the time of the addressee. In addition to the six most common constructions, there are many other syntactic constructions in newspaper headlines that are not used so often. Their existence testifies to the tendency to create a novelty of perception, the desire of journalists to overcome the automaticity of reading. This diversity to a certain extent complicates the process of reading, causes a slowdown in the process of perception and understanding. The reader needs to expend a certain effort, get used to the heading form, read the text in order to overcome the difficulties that stand in the way of adequate perception.

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